

Geometry in Engineering with STACK automatic assessment

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Abstract: STACK automatic assessment has been successfully applied in various disciplines related to engineering. In TTK UAS for several years, more and more new questions have been created to develop computational students' skills in engineering specialties. The discipline "Geometry in Engineering" as an asynchronous self-paced online course was held for the first time in the 2021/2022 academic year in the Centre for Sciences in TTK UAS based on STACK automatic assessment. This article presents the latest developments in methods for improving student-computer interaction in this discipline, using the theory of computational errors and the "STACK answer test" settings used at each node of the potential response tree (PRT) to analyse student responses.

Keywords: Asynchronous Course, Self-paced Course, Student Input.

1 Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has necessitated a transition to online learning methodologies for educational institutions worldwide. A predominant trend in the digital transformation of the education industry following the pandemic is the proliferation of distance education [Mu20]. Leveraging the adaptability of asynchronous e-learning methods employed during the pandemic, distance education has facilitated broader access to education for individuals unable to participate in conventional face-to-face classes due to various constraints. The development of computer technology has made e-learning an essential component of teaching and learning in higher education institutions around the world.

2 Background

During the 2021/2022 academic year, the Centre for Sciences of TTK UAS introduced the online course "Geometry in Engineering" for the first time. The course, taught in Estonian, was an elective subject ordered by the faculties of TTK UAS. It attracted 121 students from different specialties. The study materials consisted of theoretical materials, videos, and self-tests, with assessment tests being used to evaluate knowledge. The STACK

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automatic assessment system and Moodle's virtual learning environment were employed for creating approximately 200 STACK questions, accompanied by drawings to aid in understanding and solving geometric problems.

3 Problems and Solutions

The course lasts 16 weeks, with a weekly forum to receive feedback from students regarding the learning process. The analysis of the forum entries revealed three different types of problems associated with the elements of self-tests items. The first problem relates to questions in which students are not required to adhere to a specific problem-solving method. Since different approaches may give different approximate answers, it is important to consider not only the answer presented as a "working solution", but also answers that are roughly equivalent. In addition, to ensure standardized responses, clear instructions were given for rounding decimals in responses to each question. Unfortunately, some students did not always read the instructions carefully, which led to the second problem that arose during the tests. Finally, it is customary in Estonia to use a comma instead of a decimal point to indicate decimals. This discrepancy with the conventions was the third problem that TTK UAS students faced. To solve these problems, additional possibilities were explored for setting up questions of the STACK system.

In the current academic year, the *NumAbsolute* response verification function was implemented in STACK questions to handle floating-point responses for the first two tasks [GS22]. This involved calculating a specific tolerance value for each question. Initially, tolerance values were determined empirically using student responses and later refined through calculations. To address potential uncertainties, a note was added to the feedback provided for test questions, explaining possible causes of errors in the answers. Analysing the learning process and test answers from this academic year revealed that students no longer inquire about why their correct solutions are not considered accurate by the system, indicating a positive outcome and reduced need for clarification. To resolve the third identified issue, it is recommended that STACK system developers expand the advanced options, particularly in the *Advanced Options* section, to allow for substituting a decimal point with a comma. This modification will effectively address the problem experienced by TTK UAS students.

Bibliography

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